

The nephron physiological map and kidney disease ontologies in ONTOX project

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Abstract

Many predictive in silico models for toxicology are today available, providing accurate results for various toxicological endpoints. Even if they are animal-free approaches and avoid ethical concerns, two main issues remain unsolved: 1) the predictions are based on animal data, which does not provide the best correlation when applied to human toxicity; 2) the models are often unable to explain the biological mechanisms of toxicity because they are developed solely based on the structure of toxic and non-toxic chemicals. To overcome these limitations, a new systems biology approach has been developed, based on Physiological Maps (PM) and associated disease ontologies, aimed at reducing animal tests in the framework of ONTOX project.

I present here the PM and ontologies, as well as a workflow to assist the user in their setup, update, and validation. Starting from an expert-supervised literature review and database queries (e.g., Reactome, WikiPathways), it is possible to assemble the PM using the CellDesigner software. Secondly, the PM is visualized online by MINERVA platform, adding several layers of information (e.g., interacting chemicals, associated phenotypes, transcriptomics), and building the ontology. Finally, the PM and ontology are reviewed by experts and can be stored on the BioStudies database.

As example, the nephron PM presents the pathways for urine production, cytokines signaling, and vitamin D activation. It is associated with two ONTOX ontologies, developed to study tubular necrosis and crystallopathy. Being rich in biological mechanisms and related phenotypes, the PM and ontologies can serve for a parallel or subsequent development of adverse outcome pathways, as well as to build alterable models representing different cellular conditions. For these reasons, the PM and ontologies offer the possibility to investigate human toxicities from an innovative perspective, improving qualitatively and quantitatively the toxicological predictions.